

Research Article

A Pilot Study Using a Thematic Analysis on Challenges Faced by Working Mothers Without In-Home Assistance

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Abstract: This pilot study explores a few pertinent aspects to the issue of working mothers in Malaysian context such as the main reason they choose to become a working mother, the main challenge they faced as a working mother, the effect of being a working mother on the mother and children's mental and physical health, coping strategies of these two types of health and the future prediction of their career and family. The research employed thematic analysis using semi-structured online interview to probe these aspects among Malaysian working mothers who worked in different types of working hours namely office hour, shift hour, and freelance hour. The qualitative data revealed that: (1) financial constraint is the main reason for most women to become working mothers; (2) the main challenged face by the working mothers is the concern of their children's safety; (3) the effects of being working mothers on the mothers' mental and physical health are stress and tiredness respectively while limited time spent on their children is the effect on their children; (4) most women chose religious approach to cope with mental health while perceived house chores as exercise is the coping strategy for physical health; (5) the women predict that they will become working mothers continuously. Identifying these aspects that concern working mothers is crucial in order to sustain the working momentum, and at the same time achieve balance in terms of career and family management.

Keywords: working mothers; Malaysian context; career-family balance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In today's fast-paced world, balancing professional responsibilities with family life presents significant challenges, especially for working mothers who lack in-home assistance. These mothers juggle demanding careers while managing household tasks and childcare, often leading to overwhelming stress and burnout. The traditional family structure, in which extended families were more involved in daily caregiving, has evolved, leaving many women to manage the complications of working full-time while providing primary care for their children.

Working mothers face significant challenges in balancing their professional and family responsibilities. Time management is a major concern, with many struggling to juggle work and childcare duties (Peterson et al., 2017). The traditional gender ideology in some societies exacerbates

these challenges, as women are still viewed primarily as homemakers despite their employment status (Sultana & Noor, 2011). Work-related factors such as longer working hours, early return to work, and concerns about career consequences can increase the likelihood of perceiving work as a challenge (Peterson et al., 2017). Additionally, shift duties and lack of family support contribute to higher stress levels among working mothers (Kadale et al., 2018). The ability to exclusively breastfeed for six months is also impacted by work commitments, with only about one-third of working mothers able to do so (Kadale et al., 2018). To address these issues, organisations are encouraged to implement interventions that support working mothers (Sharma & Dhir, 2019). According to a report by the Pew Research Centre, 72% of mothers with children under 18 are now part of the workforce, and many of them struggle to find affordable and reliable childcare options (Fry, 2022). The lack of support systems exacerbates work-life balance issues, impacting both professional growth and personal well-being. Furthermore, distant or remote work blurred the barriers between professional and personal environments, disproportionately affecting working mothers especially during the COVID-19 outbreak circa 2020 (Collins et al., 2021).

Research indicates that shift work poses significant challenges for working mothers, impacting both their mental health and family dynamics. Mothers working non-day shifts experience higher levels of depressive symptoms and relationship conflict (Perry-Jenkins et al., 2007). These effects are particularly pronounced for single mothers, low-income families, and those in service occupations (Han, 2008). Shift work is associated with increased work-family conflict and psychological distress, with fathers potentially at greater risk (Zhao et al., 2020). However, even regular shifts can negatively affect mothers' mental health (Zhao et al., 2020). In India, working mothers face career barriers related to balancing maternal responsibilities and work expectations (Sharma & Dhir, 2019). Children of mothers working non-day shifts may exhibit more behavioural problems, especially in vulnerable family situations (Han, 2008). These findings underscore the need for organisational interventions to address the unique challenges faced by working mothers in various contexts (Sharma & Dhir, 2019).

The effects of this burden stemming from home are felt not only by the women themselves but also by their families and workplaces. Companies that fail to recognise and address these challenges may experience higher turnover rates, lower productivity, and decreased job satisfaction among their employees. Consequently, it is crucial for both policymakers and employers to develop solutions that alleviate the pressures faced by working mothers, promoting a more equitable and supportive environment for all. Hence, this pilot study is conducted to explore several aspects which deemed pertinent to working mothers such as (1) their reasons to become working mothers, (2) the methods they employ to manage their household, (3) their challenges they faced in their daily routine, (4) the effects of their role as working mother on their physical and mental health as well as their children, and (5) the predictions that they have if they choose to continue working.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Sampling methods and participant selection

There are twelve participants involved in this study. This number of participants even though small, it still can be accepted. Yong (2018) found that themes and codes in interview data can be identified with small samples and can still represent experiences well. This supports previous research by Hennink et al. (2016), suggesting that small sample sizes are not necessarily a limitation in qualitative research. The main focus of this pilot study is on the working women lives without the assistance of a house maid. The main objective of the pilot study is to investigate the challenges that they faced in their daily lives. All participants were selected using non-probabilities sampling method. In this study, the participants were chosen based on judgemental sampling where the working mother were selected with different types of working hours. Some of them are office hour workers, shift hour workers and

freelance workers. The various types of working hour were chosen in order to get a better generalisation of the findings produced, while recognise any significance challenges that may emerge based on their working hours.

2.2 Data Collection Method

The data for this study was collected using semi-structured online interviews. The interview process has been conducted online using Google Meet and telephone calls. This is more convenient for all respondents participating in this study. This will provide flexibility in exploring respondents' experiences and perspectives while ensuring a consistent framework across all interviews (Kallio et al., 2016). Preliminary questionnaire has been distributed to the participants so that they familiar with the background of this study.

2.3 Methodology

The collected data was analysed using thematic analysis, a widely recognized method for identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns (themes) within qualitative data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Thematic analysis was chosen because of its flexibility and its ability to provide a detailed, detailed overview of data (Nowell et al., 2017). The process involved several stages: familiarization with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the final report (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

3. FINDINGS

The interview involved working mothers which are six office hour workers, four shift hour workers, and two freelance hour workers who volunteered to participate in this study as shown in Figure 1A. The participants chosen were from various age range as illustrated in Figure 1B. The participants whose age more than 45 years old were excluded because their children were considered as adults and able to manage themselves. Based on Figure 2, no participant has more than five children. Additionally, five participants have two children which is the highest frequency while one participant has five children. In this study, working women with in-house helper were also excluded. Lastly, those who live with their parents or in laws were also excluded. This pilot study focused mainly on working women without in house helper and did not receive any assistance from their parents, in-laws or siblings. Based on the interviews with participants (refer to Table 1), the analysis produced five themes as discussed in section 3.1 until 3.5.

Figure 1A

Figure 1B

Figure 1: Demographic profile

Figure 2. Number of children a working mother have

Table 1. The demographic profile of the respondents based on working hour, age and number of children

Participants	Working Hour	Age	Number of Children
1	an office hour worker	26-30	1
2	a shift worker	36-40	4
3	an office hour worker	36-40	4
4	an office hour worker	36-40	4
5	a freelance worker	31-35	3
6	a freelance worker	31-35	2
7	a shift worker	31-35	2
8	a shift worker	26-30	1
9	a shift worker	31-35	2
10	an office hour worker	36-40	2
11	an office hour worker	41-45	2
12	an office hour worker	41-45	5

3.1 Reason being a working mother

Ten participants stated they chose to become a worker mother to help supporting family income as the main reason. Participant 2 said “My husband’s income is not enough to support our family. The cost of living is getting higher day by day. House prices are also very expensive. The house and utilities will be paid by my husband every month. On the other hand, the daily expenses, children school fees and babysitter payment are depending on me.” Based on the answer, it can be explained that the responsibility to support a family must be divided equally to both husband and wife. In the modern days, financial responsibility is not just a husband’s obligation alone due to the higher cost of living nowadays. This means that the husband’s income alone is not enough for the survival of a family. If as a mother does not work, her family will find it difficult to purchase basic necessities. As for Participant 4, she also mentioned the intention to support her family income as the main reason why she worked because she wants to improve the family life. She uttered, “My husband’s money is just enough. I must spend carefully to make sure his income enough for our small family. Therefore, by working, I can have a better house, able to eat better food, wear a better cloth, and buy all my children’s needs.” The answer from Participant 4 means that her husband money is enough to survive, but by working, she can have a pleasant family life. Apart from supporting family income, there are two

participants commented that they want to have a better future and better education for the children. Through the means of working, they can have extra money to buy more revision books and send their children to tuition centre.

The other two participants explained that they want to work because they want to fulfil their own desire and their own ambition as their first reason to work, while nine participants agree with the same reason as their second reason of being a working mother. Participant 11 proclaimed "I have my master's degree, so I feel that I must work. My parents provide me with high education, and they want me to be a successful woman. I must fulfil their dream. Besides, I can use my own money to give my parents. I do not have to ask for money from my husband." Participant 12 remarked, "I have my own desire. I want to buy a lot of things for myself and my kids. Therefore, it is easier to use my own money". In comparison to the olden days, many women have a very good education background. It would be a loss if they do not contribute their expertise as the country's skilled workforce.

Participant 9 shared a very strong reason for her to be a working mother. She wants to prepare for the worst. There are many unpredictable possibilities in the future. Women need to be prepared financially if anything happens in the household such as divorce. Usually, the children will be in the custody of their mother when such case happens. Therefore, a mother must have a backup plan especially in terms of money to raise her children. In addition, it is necessary to keep savings for the young children in case the parents passed away abruptly. Some families may also be tested with life threatening diseases that might require high treatment costs. Indeed, savings are very necessary for such emergencies.

3.2 House chores management

Ten participants mentioned that their husband and kids will help with the house chore. This shows that all parents have educated their children be a good human being. For the other two participants, they said only their husband will help because the children are still young. This finding demonstrated cooperation between husband and wife. Despite both spouses went out to earn money, the husband and wife will also help each other at home. Participant 1 responded, "When I do the house chore, my husband will look after the children. Every morning before going to work, I will dry the clothes while my husband will iron the children's uniform."

3.3 Mental and physical health

3.3.1 Mental and physical health effect to mother and children

Nine participants agreed that being a working mother can affect their mental and physical health. While two participants agree that being a working mother can affect their mental health, one participant agree with physical health. Although the choice of being a working mother could take a toll on their physical and mental health, the mothers still can handle and manage them. Participant 10 explained, "I think all women are so tired being a working mother. Sometimes, stress coming from office and a lot of house chore could cause both mental and physical pressure. But for me, I still need to be positive. My children are my strength. I must be strong". Participant 7 shared, "I choose to work, so I must manage my time wisely. At home, I have husband to support me. Some easy tasks like sweeping the floor, I will ask my children to do it. Therefore, I can focus on cooking."

As for the children, the impact of having a working mother will affect their children's mental and physical health as suggested by five participants. There are also four participants that believed their children's mental and physical are healthy with a working mother. Participant 8 asserted, "I have limited time with my children. At home I will try my best to spent time with them. I want to make sure the children know that I care about them even though I am not always around. I also believed the children understand why I must work". Having a flexible working hour is one of the benefits from

working as a freelance worker as shown by Participant 5 when she commented, “I am a freelance worker, even though my income not stable, but I can adjust my time so that I can take care my children. I do not think my work will affect their mental or physical health”.

3.3.2 Coping with mental health

The working women overcome their mental health in many ways. 11 participants agreed that praying and getting closer to religion as a first option. As a second option, eight participants chose to go for a holiday. Some of them said that they go on a holiday alone to get enough 'me-time' whereas others go on a holiday with family. Four participants preferred to read, listen, watch, or attend motivational talk as their second option. In other words, this coping method is called as bibliotherapy. Seven participants decided to express their feelings with friends as the third choice. Besides that, third option from Participant 4 asserted, “Doing what I love to do and sometimes just wandering doing nothing to free my mind”. Another interesting finding is the similar answer provided by Participant 7 and Participant 9 which is “Ignore the mess for a while”.

3.3.3 Coping with physical health

To overcome the physical health, eight participants believed that doing house chore as part of the exercise and one participant allocated her time to do exercise as their first option to handle the physical health. Another two participants opted to rest and asked help from their husband, while one participant chose gardening. As the second choice, six of them will ensure eating healthy food include taking health supplement, four participants will spend some time and some money to massage at spa and the rest choose to sleep.

3.4 Challenges in daily routine

Ten participants which are those who work office hour and shift hour stated the children's safety with a babysitter or nursery as their first fear. They did not have a choice but to let other people to take of their children. Another two participants who work as freelancers took care their own children because they work from home and have flexible working hours. Although having flexible working hours, these mothers who are also freelancers faced their own challenges. Participant 5 elaborated “I am selling cakes from home. Sometimes I received a lot of order at one time. Therefore, I need to manage my time properly and stay up the whole night to finish the order because I don't have worker to help me”.

Apart from freelancers, those working mothers who work in office hour and shift hour also specified their concerns. Participant 4 expressed, “I am office hour worker, I have to manage my time at home properly because I spent nine hours at office, then need to spend a lot of time on the road because of traffic jam”. Participant 9 added, “As a shift worker, sometimes I work in the morning shift (7am – 2pm) for two days, two days in the afternoon shift (2pm – 9pm) and night shift (9 pm – 7am) for two days as well. I really need help from the babysitter to take care of my kids. There are also times where my husband and I cannot pick my children from school, I will get help from my babysitter”.

Undeterred by these challenges, Participant 3 responded, “As a working mother, I must be strong. In the morning, I would prepare breakfast for my family. During lunch hour, I need to pick my children from their morning class, then send them again for afternoon class such as KAFA or co-curricular activities. After 5 pm, I need to pick them from school, we return home and start doing my house chores. My husband and my kids help with some of the simple house chores. With their help, I only cook for dinner. Since I do not have time to cook for lunch, usually I will just simply buy.”

3.5 Future prediction for working mothers and their family

All participants are happy being a working mother and agree that they will continue to become a working mother. Regardless of many challenges, they expressed their confidence that they can manage their family, career and health. They believed their kids can be more successful without a working mother. At the same time, they also believed that their kids can be successful with a working mother. Participant 12 foretold, "I believed my children can be successful. Even though I do not spend much time with them, I believed they know that I am always behind them, supporting them, and loving them."

4. DISCUSSION

The data obtained from the interview provided five themes which are invaluable for further discussion. From the first theme, the finding demonstrates that the main reason for these women to work instead of taking care of their children as a stay-at-home mother is financial constraint experienced by the families to sustain their living. Research by Mohd Noor and Omar (2024) has also stated financial constraint as one of the problems faced by mother-entrepreneurs along with societal stigma and work-life imbalance. Indirectly, by contributing to the household financially, working mothers can strengthen their say in household decision making (Chiew & Siow, 2023). Based on these pilot study, none of the working mothers have stated their spouse disapproval in terms of the way they managed their household.

In the second theme, it was found that these working mothers can manage their house chores with the help of their husbands and children. It is fortunate for the working mothers in this study for not having gender stereotypes because their husbands are willing to help them with the house chores and this could lead to low guilt among working mothers of not contributing more to the family (Aarntzen et al., 2022). When a wife is tired after returning from work, the husband's help, such as helping to take care of the children, cooking, and washing, will provide great relief to her heart (Hashim & Syed Mohamad, 2018). It is also essential to delegate specific tasks to the children and manage personal needs at home according to their ages (Mohd Noor & Omar, 2024). In another study for some unfortunate working mothers, the absence of emotional support from the husband is one factor that contributes to the imbalance of personal and professional lives, other factors such as the unequal distribution of household responsibilities, such as cooking, cleaning, and managing the home, as well as caring for children and other chores (Salleh et al., 2023). Hence, shared household responsibilities led women to experience less conflict between their gender and work identity (Uddin, 2021).

The finding from the third theme indicates that being a working mother can affect mental and physical health for them and their children. Research by Salleh et al. (2023) has shown that work-family conflict is a source of stress and has been linked to negative effects such as increased health risks, less effective parenting, decreased productivity, tardiness, absenteeism, poor attitudes and morale, reduced life satisfaction, and lower mental health. To cope with their mental health, most women opted for praying and getting closer to religion. Regardless of the coping strategies, it is important for mothers to take care of their mental health as children of mothers with depression are more likely to experience cognitive and physical growth delays, academic challenges, and mental health concerns when compared to children raised by mothers with no mental health diagnosis (Wachs et al., 2009; as cited in McKinney & Meinersmann, 2022). As for coping with their physical health, these women viewed doing house chores as a form of exercise instead of seeing the chores as burden. By doing this, it indicates that the working mothers are being mindful of their internal states and surroundings. After all, mindfulness

can help overcome fatigue, uncertainty and overwork (Segev, 2023). In this regard, women's self-motivation and mental and physical strength are the primary keys to their capabilities (Hjálmsdóttir & Bjarnadóttir, 2021).

The fourth theme presented the challenges faced by working mothers and they are in consensus that the safety of their children is their utmost fear. In a study conducted by Mohd Yusoff et al. (2021), they found that Malaysian women with children would rather leave the labour force and fulfil their responsibility as a wife and mothers even if they are graduates from university and hence, the lower female labour force participation rate in Malaysia. However, for the working women in this study, although they are afraid about their children's safety, they continued to work because there has been evidence that reveals the economic empowerment of women results in a substantial development in children's health, nutrition, education, and future career, which has multiplier effects on the sustainable development of a country (Jones et al., 2010; as cited in Uddin et al., 2021). Women's development enhances their bargaining power and control over resources, enabling them to make greater investments to improve their and their children's quality of life and wellbeing.

Finally, the fifth theme shown that these women will continue to become working mothers in spite of piling house chores, mental and physical health concerns as well as daily challenges. This theme can be related to the working motivation among working mothers. This study revealed that the working motivation among Malaysian working mothers were understudied. In American context, mothers become demotivated to work if the maternity leave policy did not benefit them (Zhang & Rodrigue, 2023). In India, mothers become demotivated to work when they have to commute for a distance to their office (Tayal & Mehta, 2023) and inability to achieve work-life balance (Rawal, 2023).

5. CONCLUSION

The involvement of women in workforce are undeniably pertinent in the modern era. Thus, by exploring and understanding their reasons to continue working, methods to manage house chores, impacts on their mental and physical health, their challenges and future predictions of their career, it indicates that Malaysian women in general are able to withstand all the difficulties that might emerge from their personal and professional lives. Besides, there is also a need for future research to investigate the internal and external motivation factors which drive Malaysian working mothers to continue working.

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